

SintesiPaperopoli.R

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Mon Apr 11 11:16:41 2016

```
#Summary of the analysis for Paperopoli's rainfall  
# It is not the best way to do it in R but it works  
#The data below are copied by hands  
a1h<-31.59047  
b1h<-9.073165  
a3h<-39.18705  
b3h<-10.69436  
a6h<-48.10011  
b6h<-12.39947  
a12h <- 60.5621  
b12h <-18.00545  
a24h <-75.84853  
b24h <-22.43485  
x <- seq(from=1, to = 200, by =1)  
#Plotting the P[H <h]  
library("evd")
```

```
## Warning: package 'evd' was built under R version 3.2.3
```

```
plot(x,pgumbel(x,a1h,b1h),type="l",col="black",lwd=2,xlab="h [mm]", ylab="P[H < h]",main="Curve di Gumbel")  
lines(x,pgumbel(x,a3h,b3h),type="l",col="red",lwd=2)  
lines(x,pgumbel(x,a6h,b6h),type="l",col="blue",lwd=2)  
lines(x,pgumbel(x,a12h,b12h),type="l",col="darkgreen",lwd=2)  
lines(x,pgumbel(x,a24h,b24h),type="l",col="skyblue",lwd=2)
```

Curve di Gumbel di Paperopoli


```
#Plotting the p[h]  
plot(x,dgumbel(x,a1h,b1h),type="l",col="black",lwd=2,xlab="h [mm]", ylab="P[H < h]",main="Curve di Gumbel")  
lines(x,dgumbel(x,a3h,b3h),type="l",col="red",lwd=2)  
lines(x,dgumbel(x,a6h,b6h),type="l",col="blue",lwd=2)  
lines(x,dgumbel(x,a12h,b12h),type="l",col="darkgreen",lwd=2)  
lines(x,dgumbel(x,a24h,b24h),type="l",col="skyblue",lwd=2)
```

Curve di Gumbel di Paperopoli


```
p <- 1-1/10
p
```

```
## [1] 0.9
```

```
durations <-c(1,3,6,12,24)
quantiles <- c(1-1/10,1-1/50,1-1/100)
h1<-c(qgumbel(quantiles,a1h,b1h))
h3<-c(qgumbel(quantiles,a3h,b3h))
h6<-c(qgumbel(quantiles,a6h,b6h))
h12<-c(qgumbel(quantiles,a12h,b12h))
h24<-c(qgumbel(quantiles,a24h,b24h))
h1
```

```
## [1] 52.00842 66.99340 73.32838
```

```
#Plotting the LSPP 10
ten<-c(h1[1],h3[1],h6[1],h12[1],h24[1])
ten
```

```
## [1] 52.00842 63.25329 76.00347 101.08098 126.33518
```

```
plot(durations,ten,log="xy")
```



```
lm(log(ten) ~ log(durations)) -> lr10
lr10
```

```
##
## Call:
## lm(formula = log(ten) ~ log(durations))
##
## Coefficients:
## (Intercept) log(durations)
## 3.8891 0.2851
```

```
lr10$coefficients[1]
```

```
## (Intercept)
## 3.889117
```

```
lr10$coefficients[2]
```

```
## log(durations)
## 0.2851059
```

```
z <- seq(from=0.99,to=50,by=0.25)
plot(z,exp(lr10$coefficients[1])*z^lr10$coefficients[2],type="l",log="xy",col="dark red",lwd=2,xlab="du
points(durations,ten,pch=0)
#LSPP 50
fifty <- c(h1[2],h3[2],h6[2],h12[2],h24[2])
lm(log(fifty) ~ log(durations)) -> lr50
lr50
```

```
##
```

```
## Call:
## lm(formula = log(fifty) ~ log(durations))
##
## Coefficients:
##      (Intercept)  log(durations)
##           4.1362           0.2872
```

```
lr50$coefficients[1]
```

```
## (Intercept)
##      4.136192
```

```
lr50$coefficients[2]
```

```
## log(durations)
##           0.2871788
```

```
lines(z,exp(lr50$coefficients[1])*z^lr50$coefficients[2],col="blue")
points(durations,fifty,pch=2)
#LSP 100
hundred <- c(h1[3],h3[3],h6[3],h12[3],h24[3])
lm(log(hundred) ~ log(durations)) -> lr100
lr100
```

```
##
## Call:
## lm(formula = log(hundred) ~ log(durations))
##
## Coefficients:
##      (Intercept)  log(durations)
##           4.2247           0.2878
```

```
lr100$coefficients[1]
```

```
## (Intercept)
##      4.224702
```

```
lr100$coefficients[2]
```

```
## log(durations)
##           0.2877995
```

```
lines(z,exp(lr100$coefficients[1])*z^lr100$coefficients[2],col="dark green")
points(durations,hundred,pch=1)
```

